

Ultrasound Evaluation of Rotator Cuff Injuries & Their Correlation with Magnetic Resonance Imaging

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Abstract:

Background: Shoulder discomfort is a prevalent global health issue, affecting 16-26% of the population. Rotator cuff disease, a common cause of shoulder pain, has seen evolving treatment strategies, including both surgical and non-surgical options. Diagnostic imaging is crucial in managing rotator cuff disorders, with ultrasound (USG) and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) being primary modalities. While MRI is the gold standard, USG offers a cost-effective and accessible alternative.

Introduction: This study aims to evaluate the efficacy of USG and MRI in diagnosing rotator cuff tendon abnormalities. USG is favoured for its affordability and convenience, though its diagnostic sensitivity and specificity vary. MRI provides detailed insights but is more costly and less accessible. This study compares these imaging modalities in terms of their diagnostic accuracy for rotator cuff tears.

Methodology: A cross-sectional study was conducted over two years at ERA's Medical College, Lucknow. Forty patients aged 18 and above, suspected of rotator cuff pathology, were included. Patients underwent both USG and MRI evaluations. Exclusion criteria included recent shoulder surgery, ongoing treatment for rotator cuff lesions, and MRI contraindications. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS software to compare the diagnostic efficacy of USG and MRI.

Results: MRI identified partial thickness supraspinatus tears in 57.50% and full thickness in 30.00% of patients. USG detected partial thickness supraspinatus tears in 54.84% and full thickness in 35.48%. For partial thickness supraspinatus tears, USG showed a sensitivity of 65.22%, specificity of 88.24%, and an accuracy of 75.00%. For full thickness supraspinatus tears, USG had a sensitivity of 83.33%, specificity of 96.43%, and an accuracy of 92.50%. The agreement between USG and MRI ranged from moderate to substantial, with Kappa values of 0.511 for partial thickness and 0.817 for full thickness supraspinatus tears.

Conclusion: MRI remains the gold standard for diagnosing rotator cuff tears. However, USG demonstrates substantial promise as an effective and cost-effective alternative, particularly for assessing supraspinatus tears. The study highlights that rotator cuff injuries predominantly affect younger males and right-sided shoulders. Incorporating USG into routine orthopedic practice, especially in settings with limited MRI access, could improve early diagnosis and patient outcomes.

Keywords: Rotator Cuff Tears, Ultrasound (USG), Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI), Diagnostic Imaging, Shoulder Pain, Orthopedic Practice.

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Introduction

Shoulder discomfort is a significant global health issue, affecting between 16% and 26% of the population, with an annual incidence rate of 14.7 per 1,000 patients [1,2]. This condition is the third most common musculoskeletal complaint in orthopaedic practice, following knee and back pain [3]. In India, shoulder pain is particularly prevalent, affecting 7.4% of rural residents compared to 2% of urban populations [4]. Rotator cuff disease, a common cause of shoulder pain, is increasingly prevalent, especially among the ageing population. Treatment strategies for rotator cuff tears have

evolved significantly over the past three decades, emphasizing techniques such as restoring the anatomic footprint, utilizing margin convergence, and repairing subscapularis tears. While physical therapy has shown effectiveness in managing full-thickness tears nonoperatively, patients with massive, irreparable injuries face challenges. Synthetic or biological grafting has emerged as a promising treatment option, although more data is needed to assess its long-term effectiveness [5]. Diagnostic imaging plays a crucial role in managing rotator cuff disease, with ultrasound

(USG) and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) being the primary modalities. USG is favoured for its low cost, non-invasiveness, and accessibility, but its diagnostic sensitivity and specificity vary widely, ranging from above 90% to below 50%. MRI, on the other hand, is considered the gold standard for rotator cuff imaging, with consistently high specificity (93-94%) and sensitivity (80-97%). MRI provides detailed insights into tear characteristics, muscle atrophy, and other critical factors but has limitations such as high cost, limited accessibility, and contraindications for certain patients [6].

Shoulder ultrasound is increasingly recognized for its accuracy in detecting rotator cuff injuries, with some studies suggesting comparable accuracy to MRI [7]. However, its effectiveness is highly dependent on the operator's skill due to the shoulder's complex anatomy. Although there is limited research on observer agreement in shoulder ultrasound, some studies have shown high agreement among experienced radiologists, particularly for full-thickness tears. A consensus by the Society of Radiologists in Ultrasound suggests that utilizing algorithms for imaging evaluation can improve patient care and reduce unnecessary costs [1]. This study aims to assess various etiological factors contributing to acute and chronic shoulder pain, investigate the practicality of ultrasonography in the diagnosis of rotator cuff disorders, and set it against MRI in terms of sensitivity and specificity. While MRI remains a highly effective diagnostic tool, the practicality and cost-effectiveness of ultrasound make it a valuable alternative, especially in settings where MRI may not be feasible. Therefore, it would be beneficial to utilise a readily accessible and cost-effective modality such as ultrasound as the primary imaging tool in the majority of instances.

Material and Methods

This cross-sectional study will be conducted over a period of two years at the Department of Orthopaedic Surgery and the Department of Radio Diagnosis at ERA's Medical College, Lucknow. The study aims to evaluate the efficacy of ultrasound (USG) and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) in diagnosing rotator cuff tendon abnormalities. A total of 40 patients, aged 18 and above, who are suspected clinically of having shoulder pathology and referred for USG and MRI evaluation, will be included in the study. The inclusion criteria specify that only those patients who show abnormalities in the rotator cuff tendons will be part of the study. However, patients who have undergone recent shoulder surgery (within six weeks), those already receiving treatment for known rotator cuff lesions, and those with contraindications for MRI, such as individuals with electrically or mechanically activated implants, will

be excluded. The sample size was determined using a sensitivity of 0.95 for USG, a prevalence rate of 0.5 for rotator cuff abnormalities, and a precision of 0.10, with a 95% confidence level. The calculated sample size was 37, which was adjusted to 40 to account for potential data loss.

The study will begin with a thorough clinical evaluation conducted in the Department of Orthopaedics, where patient demographics, the side of involvement, and the extent of impairment will be documented. After obtaining informed consent, patients will undergo imaging evaluation using advanced ultrasound technology (Samsung HS70A) and MRI (Magnetom Vida 3T with biomatrix technology). Images will be processed and analyzed using Syngovia software, with radiologists evaluating the findings. Statistical analysis will be performed on the collected data to draw conclusions regarding the effectiveness of USG and MRI in diagnosing rotator cuff abnormalities, thereby providing valuable insights into the comparative utility of these imaging modalities.

Statistical Analysis: SPSS software (SPSS Inc., Chicago, IL, USA) was used for statistical analysis with the Windows program (26.0 version).

Results

The study enrolled 40 patients to assess the agreement between ultrasound (USG) and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) in detecting rotator cuff tears. The age distribution of the patients showed that the majority fell within the 18-30 years age group, representing 27.50% of the sample, followed by the 30-39 years group at 25.00%. Age groups 50-59 years and 60-65 years each comprised 17.50% of the patients, while the 40-49 years group was the least represented, accounting for 12.50%. In terms of gender distribution, males made up a significant proportion, with 67.50% (27 patients), while females constituted 32.50% (13 patients) (Table 1).

Regarding the patients' pain and trauma history, 65.00% (26 patients) had a history of trauma, making it the most common factor. A combination of pain, restricted range of motion (RRROM), and trauma was reported by 7.50% (3 patients), while pain with RRROM but without trauma was noted in 20.00% (8 patients). Pain alone was reported by 7.50% (3 patients). Laterality analysis revealed that right-sided injuries were more prevalent, affecting 70.00% (28 patients), while left-sided injuries were present in 30.00% (12 patients) (Table 2).

The study's findings on rotator cuff tears highlighted the diagnostic capabilities of MRI and USG. MRI identified partial thickness supraspinatus tears in 57.50% of patients, while USG detected these tears in 54.84% of cases. Full

thickness supraspinatus tears were observed in 30.00% of patients via MRI and in 35.48% of patients via USG (Figure 1). The agreement between USG and MRI was analyzed, revealing a moderate Kappa agreement of 0.511 for partial thickness supraspinatus tears. The sensitivity of USG in detecting these tears was 65.22%, with a specificity of 88.24%, and an overall accuracy of 75.00% (Table 3).

For full thickness supraspinatus tears, USG demonstrated a substantial agreement with MRI, with a Kappa value of 0.817. The sensitivity of USG for these tears was 83.33%, specificity was 96.43%, and the overall accuracy was 92.50% (Table 3). The agreement between USG and MRI

for partial thickness infraspinatus tears was also substantial, with a Kappa value of 0.787. The sensitivity of USG for these tears was 66.67%, and the specificity was 100%, with an accuracy of 96.57% (Table 4). Finally, for partial thickness subscapularis tears, USG showed substantial agreement with MRI, with a Kappa value of 0.655, a sensitivity of 50.00%, and an accuracy of 97.50% (Table 5).

These findings underscore the effectiveness of USG in detecting rotator cuff tears, particularly full-thickness tears, while also highlighting the moderate to substantial agreement with MRI in diagnosing these conditions.

Table 1: Socio demographic distribution of enrolled patients

Socio demographic parameters		N=40	%
Age (Years)	18-30	11	27.50%
	30-39	10	25.00%
	40-49	5	12.50%
	50-59	7	17.50%
	60-65	7	17.50%
Gender	Female	13	32.50%
	Male	27	67.50%

Table 2: History and laterality of enrolled patients

Parameters		N=40	%
History	Pain	3	7.50%
	Pain + RROM	8	20.00%
	Pain + RROM + Trauma	3	7.50%
	Trauma	26	65.00%
Laterality	Left	12	30.00%
	RIGHT	28	70.00%

Figure 1: Graphical Representation of MRI and USG Findings in Rotator Cuff Tears in enrolled patients

Table 3: Agreement between USG and MRI in Detecting Partial and Full Thickness Supraspinatus Tear

Partial Thickness Supraspinatus Tear	USG [N=17]	MRI Findings [N=23]		Total (Row)
		+	-	
		+	15	2
-	8	15	23	
Total (Column)		23	17	40
Kappa Agreement		0.511 [Moderate Agreement]		
Sensitivity		65.22% [42.73% - 83.62%]		
Specificity		88.24% [63.56% - 98.54%]		
PPV		88.24% [66.36% - 96.61%]		
NPV		65.22% [51.07% - 77.11%]		
Accuracy		75.00% [58.80% - 87.31%]		

Full Thickness Supraspinatus Tear	USG [N=11]	MRI Findings [N=12]		Total (Row)
		+	-	
		+	10	1
-	2	27	29	
Total (Column)		12	28	40
Kappa Agreement		0.817 [Substantial Agreement]		
Sensitivity		83.33% [51.59% - 97.91%]		
Specificity		96.43% [81.65% - 99.91%]		
PPV		90.91% [58.94% - 98.59%]		
NPV		93.10% [79.18% - 97.96%]		
Accuracy		92.50% [79.61% - 98.43%]		

Table 4: Agreement between USG and MRI in Detecting Partial Thickness Infrapinatus Tear

Partial Thickness Infrapinatus Tear	MRI Findings [N=3]		Total (Row)
USG [N=2]	+	-	
+	2	0	2
-	1	37	38
Total (Column)		3	37
Kappa Agreement		0.787 [Substantial Agreement]	
Sensitivity		66.67% [9.43% - 99.16%]	
Specificity		100.00% [90.51% - 100.00%]	
PPV		100.00% [88.19% - 99.46%]	
NPV		97.37% [88.19% - 99.46%]	
Accuracy		96.57% [87.84% - 99.67%]	

Table 5: Agreement between USG and MRI in Detecting Partial Thickness Subscapularis Tear

Partial Thickness Subscapularis Tear	MRI Findings [N=2]		Total (Row)
USG [N=1]	+	-	
+	1	0	1
-	1	38	39
Total (Column)		2	38
Kappa Agreement		0.655 [Substantial Agreement]	
Sensitivity		50.00% [1.26% - 98.74%]	
Specificity		100.00% [90.75% - 100.00%]	
PPV		100.00% [2.50% - 100.00%]	
NPV		97.44% [90.48% - 99.35%]	
Accuracy		97.50% [86.84% - 99.94%]	

Figure 2: PDFS coronal view of shoulder showing full thickness supraspinatus tear with retraction of fibers (marked with red line)

Figure 3: Full thickness tear of supraspinatus (white arrow) showing retraction of supraspinatus tendon fibers (white line)

Discussion

Rotator cuff issues, particularly involving the supraspinatus tendon, are the most common causes of shoulder pain, including tendinosis and partial or full-thickness tears [8,9]. Wherein 52 patients and 44 USG patients were found to have pathologies of the supraspinatus tendon. This is consistent with a study by Zlatkin et al. [8] that discovered supraspinatus tendon involvement in about 80% of the cases. According to Vinay et al. [10] the USG criteria for partial thickness tear detection were focal tendon discontinuity at the articular or bursal margin. Full-thickness rotator cuff tears were identified on USG by the absence of the tendon, with the subacromial-subdeltoid bursa and deltoid

muscle filling the space over the humeral head. Tendinosis appeared as heterogeneous echotexture and tendon thinning on USG. MRI showed partial tears as fiber discontinuity with fluid signal, while full-thickness tears were characterized by tendon discontinuity and retraction.

In this study, the most represented age group is 18-30 years (27.50%), followed by 30-39 years (25.00%). Males make up 67.50% of the sample, while females comprise 32.50%. A majority of patients (65.00%) have a history of trauma, with 20.00% reporting pain with restricted range of motion (RRROM) without trauma. Right-sided injuries are more prevalent, occurring in 70.00% of cases, compared to 30.00% on the left side.

According to Farooqi et al. [11] 60% of the patients were between the ages of 40 and 50, 26.7% were between the ages of 51 and 60, and the remaining 13.3% were older than 60. The study included patients with an average age of 49.77 years (SD: 10.27), with 53.3% men and 46.7% women. Shoulder pain duration was up to one month in 43.3% of patients, one to six months in 43.3%, and six to twelve months in 13.3%. Right shoulder involvement was seen in 70% of cases, and all patients were right-handed. Diabetes was present in 30% of patients, and 16.67% had a history of trauma. Physical examination showed tenderness in 16.67% of patients, 23.3% had a 45-degree range of motion restriction, and Neer's test was positive in 43.3% of cases.

The study found that MRI identified partial thickness supraspinatus tears in 57.50% of cases (23 patients), while USG detected them in 54.84% (17 patients). Full thickness supraspinatus tears were found in 30.00% (12 patients) by MRI and 35.48% (11 patients) by USG. For partial thickness infraspinatus tears, MRI detected 7.50% (3 patients) and USG detected 6.45% (2 patients). Partial thickness subscapularis tears were identified in 5.00% (2 patients) by MRI and 3.23% (1 patient) by USG. Previous literatures have indicated that operator skill for both image acquisition and interpretation plays a major role in the diagnostic capacity of US for rotator cuff pathology [12,13]. Three studies showed that the more scans performed by less experienced operators, the better the accuracy, sensitivity, and specificity of US for supraspinatus tears [14-16]. Rutten et al. [7] showed that even with differing levels of experience, both a radiologist with MSK training and one without identified full- and partial-thickness supraspinatus tears equally well in 200 patients.

Other studies suggest that receiving feedback from surgical outcomes improves operator performance and accelerates training. Kurz et al. [17] discovered that after participating in arthroscopy procedures and going over the related surgical reports, an experienced MSK sonographer increased the sensitivity from 93% to 99% and the specificity from 68% to 93% for detecting supraspinatus tears. Likewise, Iossifidis et al. [14] and Murphy et al. [15] found that shoulder surgeons could achieve sensitivity and specificity for full-thickness supraspinatus tears comparable to experienced MSK radiologists after just 50 to 140 scans, especially when surgery was performed on the same day as the US exam.

This suggests that US proficiency can be achieved earlier than the 250-300 scan minimum recommended by radiological bodies for radiologists without access to subsequent surgical reports [17]. In the current study, USG detected 2

out of 3 MRI-confirmed partial thickness infraspinatus tears, with a substantial agreement (Kappa 0.787) between USG and MRI. USG showed a sensitivity of 66.67%, specificity of 100%, and overall accuracy of 96.57%. Fischer et al. [18] reported that USG missed no full-thickness infraspinatus tears, with a sensitivity of 0.88 and specificity of 0.86 for detecting any infraspinatus tendon damage. MRI matched intraoperative findings in 86.7% of cases, while USG matched in 91.1%, with both modalities accurately identifying full-thickness tears.

In our study, USG correctly identified 1 out of 2 MRI-confirmed partial thickness subscapularis tears, missing 1 case. Among 38 patients without tears on MRI, USG had no false positives. The agreement between USG and MRI was substantial (Kappa 0.655), with USG showing a sensitivity of 50%, specificity of 100%, and overall accuracy of 97.50%. TE Farley et al. [19] noted that fluid in the subacromial-subdeltoid bursa could indicate a full-thickness tear. Vinay et al. [9] found USG had a 10% detection rate for subscapularis pathology, compared to MRI's 6.7%.

In our study, USG accurately identified 10 of 12 MRI-confirmed tears, with a Kappa value of 0.817, indicating substantial agreement. USG had a sensitivity of 83.33%, specificity of 96.43%, and overall accuracy of 92.50%. For partial thickness tears, sensitivity was 65.22% and specificity 88.24%. Farley et al. [19] reported similar findings, with USG detecting 73.3% and MRI 86.7% of supraspinatus pathologies. US has been shown by Farooqi et al. [11] to be a dependable and useful imaging modality for the diagnosis of rotator cuff tears. Despite US's lower sensitivity for partial tears, it remains cost-effective and convenient compared to MRI. Recent studies indicate improved US diagnostic accuracy over the past five years, making it a valuable tool for rotator cuff injuries [11,20-23].

In the present study, among the 3 patients with MRI-confirmed tears, USG correctly identified 2 (true positives) and missed 1 (false negative). Among the 37 patients without tears on MRI, USG correctly identified all 37 (true negatives) with no false positives. The analysis indicates substantial agreement between USG and MRI, with a Kappa value of 0.787. USG's sensitivity is 66.67%, specificity is 100%, positive predictive value (PPV) is 100%, negative predictive value (NPV) is 97.37%, and overall accuracy is 96.57%. Though most prior US research has concentrated on supraspinatus and infraspinatus tendon imaging, concurrent subscapularis tendon tears are relatively common; literature reports finding them in about half of all rotator cuff repairs. [98,99] According to three investigations, US showed low sensitivity (0.13-0.39) and high specificity (0.93-1.00) for

diagnosing full and partial subscapularis tears. [100-102] According to Denard et al., [24] one of the most likely important factors contributing to the low sensitivity for subscapularis tears is the decreased US access to the subscapularis region in comparison to the other rotator cuff tendons. According to Adams et al. [25] report, MRI has a similarly low sensitivity for diagnosing subscapularis tears, according to earlier research. Skendzel et al. [26] found that while diagnosing full-thickness tears in LHB tendons and tendons free of pathology could be done with high accuracy, it was difficult to differentiate partial-thickness LHB tendon tears from other pathologies like tendinosis and tenosynovitis.

There is a dearth of research in the literature evaluating the LHB tendon and the subscapularis via US evaluation, and more research is required to establish the precise diagnostic accuracy of US. There is a dearth of research in the literature evaluating the LHB tendon and the subscapularis via US evaluation, and more research is required to establish the precise diagnostic accuracy of US. As US has a low sensitivity and a high specificity for biceps and subscapularis tendon tears, we recommend using it as a confirmatory diagnostic imaging modality in patients suspected of having a pathology rather than for patient screening.

Finally, the study emphasizes how important it is to use diagnostic imaging methods, particularly MRI and ultrasound (USG), when evaluating rotator cuff tears. The results highlight higher prevalence among males and specific age groups, as well as noteworthy trends across various demographic groups. Crucially, the significant to moderate agreements found between USG and MRI for various tear types highlight how trustworthy both modalities are in clinical situations. These insights not only support precise diagnosis but also direct treatment choices, guaranteeing proper care catered to the specific requirements of each patient. Therefore, continued investigation and improvement of imaging technologies keep them more effective, which eventually improves patient outcomes in orthopedic practice.

Conclusion

The study concludes that while MRI remains the gold standard for diagnosing shoulder injuries, ultrasound (USG) demonstrates considerable promise as an effective alternative, particularly for assessing supraspinatus tears. The substantial agreement between MRI and USG findings, with high sensitivity and specificity for detecting both full and partial thickness tears, highlights the reliability of USG as a diagnostic tool. Additionally, the study reveals that these injuries predominantly affect a younger demographic, with a higher incidence in males and right-sided injuries.

Integrating USG into orthopedic practice, especially in settings with limited MRI access, could significantly enhance the early diagnosis and treatment of shoulder injuries, leading to improved patient outcomes and more efficient use of healthcare resources.

Consent: Written informed consent has been obtained from all participants in accordance with international or university standards and is maintained by the authors.

Ethical Approval: Ethical approval was granted in compliance with international or university standards, and the written approval is preserved by the authors.

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